

HPC-JEEP: Energy Usage on ARCHER2 and the DiRAC COSMA HPC services

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1. Introduction

National supercomputing and HPC services such as [ARCHER2](#) and [DiRAC](#) represent large investments in DRI by UKRI to serve UK research and use large amounts of electricity (for example, ARCHER2 is capable of drawing ~4 MW at peak load). Traditionally, resources on such services have been granted in units of compute time (core-hours, node-hours, etc.) with users not informed, nor paying much attention to their energy use; and services not generally reporting breakdowns of energy use other than for total electricity charges. Without an understanding of how research areas, projects and users use energy and how efficiently they use resources it is difficult to plan future procurements or service strategies towards a net zero goal. The HPC-JEEP project is looking at what level of energy information can be extracted from current and historical per-job data from ARCHER2 and DiRAC services; and how this data can be analysed and synthesised to provide the information required for funders (who procure and set service strategy and objectives) and researchers (who make decisions about how best to use the resources they are granted) to allow them to make informed decisions about how to manage HPC resources to extract the maximum research benefit in the most emissions efficient way. The challenges the project is trying to address are:

1. What evidence can we provide from current HPC energy usage data to support users and funders towards net zero?
2. What could be the potential impacts of moving to job charging based on energy/emissions use to support net zero goals based on current evidence?
3. What are the best energy/emissions metrics that could be provided to HPC users and funders to help them support net zero goals?

In this report we address primarily Challenge 1: *What evidence can we provide from current HPC energy usage data to support users and funders towards net zero?*. In particular, we have taken data that can be extracted currently from the ARCHER2 and DiRAC COSMA national HPC services and performed work to try and gain an understanding of what types of analyses and conclusions are supported.

Any emissions from the energy used by both ARCHER2 and DiRAC COSMA are Scope 2 emissions as the energy is drawn from the UK National Grid. Using job energy use data to estimate Scope 2 emissions is a future goal of the HPC-JEEP project and is not considered further in this report.

The paper is laid out in the following way: Section 2 provides a brief overview of the ARCHER2 and DiRAC COSMA systems and a breakdown of power draw by different hardware components, Section 3 describes the methodologies used to extract and analyse the energy use data; Section 4 presents our analyses of energy use data; Section 5 provides some conclusions from the work so far and thoughts on implications of the rest of the project. The whole paper is supported by a dataset containing the raw data that was used for the analysis and the scripts and tooling that performed the analysis itself¹.

¹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7128646>

2. Hardware Details

ARCHER2

ARCHER2 is the UK national supercomputing service funded by UKRI (via EPSRC and NERC) with the HPC platform provided by HPE and the hosting and support provided by EPCC at The University of Edinburgh. The ARCHER2 system is a liquid-cooled HPE Cray EX with 5,860 compute nodes giving a total of 750,080 compute cores. ARCHER2 is one of the largest HPC systems without GPU accelerators in the world and sits at #25 in the June 2022 Top500 list of supercomputers. As well as the hardware platform, the ARCHER2 service provides a range of support for users and beyond, including a team of expert RSEs at EPCC to provide support for the research community, an extensive training programme and an outreach component. ARCHER2 is a general-purpose service supporting a wide range of research communities and software with a corresponding wide range of technical requirements and use cases.

The technical data on ARCHER2 energy use and power draw used here are taken from the ARCHER2 Case Study activity in the UKRI Net Zero DRI Scoping project².

Compute nodes

The ARCHER2 compute nodes are CPU only (i.e. they do not have any GPU accelerators available) with a total of 128 physical CPU cores per node. There are 5860 compute nodes, each with:

- 2x AMD EPYC™ 7742 64c 2.25 GHz processors
- 256/512 GB DDR4 memory
- 2x 100 Gbps Slingshot 10 interconnect interfaces (one per processor)

Interconnect

- HPE Cray Slingshot 10 - ethernet based, dynamic routing
- Dragonfly topology - maximum of 3 hops between any two compute nodes
- 768 switches in the whole system

Storage

- 3x ClusterStor L300 Lustre file systems, each 3.6 PB
- 1 PB ClusterStor E1000 solid state storage
- 4x NetApp FAS8200A file systems, 1 PB total

Power profile

Based on data from HPE, we have the following estimates of power draw for components:

² <https://net-zero-dri.ceda.ac.uk/archer/>

- Slingshot interconnect switches: approx. 700 W per switch, 768 switches in the system, 540 kW in total
- ClusterStor Lustre file systems: approx. 8 kW per file system, 5 file systems in system, 40 kW in total
- Cooling Distribution Units (CDU): 16 kW per CDU, 6 CDU in the system, 96 kW in total

Given that each compute node has an estimated maximum power draw of around 600 W and there are 5860 compute nodes, this gives a total maximum power draw for the compute nodes of around 3,500 kW. This, in turn, gives an estimated maximum power draw for the ARCHER2 system of over 4,000 kW with the following rough percentage breakdown by component:

- Compute nodes: 83%
- Slingshot interconnect switches: 14%
- CDU: 2%
- ClusterStor Lustre file systems: 1%

This breakdown indicates that the node energy use is by far the most significant component of energy use for jobs on the ARCHER2 system. For large jobs there may be some contribution from interconnect use, but file system energy use is a negligible component for all jobs.

One observation from ARCHER2 is that the compute node idle power draw is a large fraction of the peak power draw. An idle compute node on ARCHER2 typically draws 200 to 250 W (around 40% of the 600 W peak power draw). The processors typically draw around 40 W on an idle node and the memory around 115 W. We assume that the remaining idle power draw (around 100 W) is mostly due to the Slingshot interconnect cards. On ARCHER2, this does not lead to issues with excess energy use as the utilisation is so high (over 90%) but, if the system was less busy, this would lead to a large power draw even if the system was not being used. The ARCHER2 service is working with HPE to understand how this high idle compute node power draw can be reduced. The majority of the difference between idle and active power use on an ARCHER2 compute node is the change in power draw of the processors: each processor has an idle power draw of around 20 W and, when loaded, can draw up to 225 W³.

This energy consumption is in-system only, and thus does not include inefficiencies due to the plant behind the hardware; e.g. UPS (ARCHER2 compute nodes are not on UPS, they are on raw electricity feeds) and external cooling infrastructure.

DiRAC COSMA

The DiRAC Memory Intensive system, COSMA is a UK national HPC facility funded by UKRI via STFC. It is a Dell system operated by the Institute for Computational Cosmology at Durham University. The latest instantiation of COSMA, COSMA8, is comprised of 360 compute nodes (46k cores), using AMD EPYC™ 7H12 processors and direct liquid cooling. COSMA is aimed at memory intensive workloads with 1 TB RAM per node.

³ <https://www.amd.com/en/products/cpu/amd-epyc-7742>

Compute nodes

CPU-only, 360 compute nodes each with:

- 2x AMD EPYC™ 7H12 64c 2.6 GHz processors
- 1 TB DDR4 memory
- 1x 200 Gbps InfiniBand interface

Interconnect

A non-blocking fat tree topology of HDR 200 Gbps InfiniBand, using 20 spine switches and 24 leaf switches.

Storage

- 5.3 PB Lustre file system using Dell ME484 JBODs and a self-installed Lustre file system. 4 MDS and 6 OSS servers, 6 JBODs each with 84x 16 TB disks
- 1.2 PB fast NVMe file system using Dell R640 servers

Power profile

- The InfiniBand switches consume about 350 W, 15 kW total (44 switches)
- The COSMA8 bulk storage consumes about 8 kW.
- The COSMA8 fast storage consumes about 10 kW.
- The cooling distribution units consume about 1 kW.

These values were taken from live PDU measurements and represent that of the live system.

The compute nodes consume between 150 to 850 W depending on job, and average power of the compute node racks is about 175 kW (averaged between Feb-Sept 2022). This includes leaf and Ethernet switches, so removing these gives about 167 kW for the compute nodes alone. Total power consumption for the whole system excluding the CDUs is 210 kW. The remainder is additional facilities such as login nodes, DINE and fat nodes (including GPU nodes).

Therefore, we have:

- Compute: 80%
- Storage: 9%
- Fabric: 7%
- CDU: 0.5%
- Remainder: 3%

Idle power of a COSMA8 node is about 150 W, and they can consume up to 850 W (occasionally 900 W) when in use. Therefore, idle consumption is only about 17% of maximum consumption. The average power consumption is about 450 W. Utilisation of compute nodes is high, greater than 90%.

This energy consumption is in-data-centre only, and thus does not include inefficiencies due to UPS or the free air coolers and active chillers.

Every quarter, information about their energy usage is emailed to each COSMA user, and a summary sent to the project PIs. The aim of this is to raise user awareness, provide useful and insightful information about their net-zero impacts, and also provide tools with which future allocation estimates can be obtained.

3. Methodology

ARCHER2

On ARCHER2, the node energy data is taken from the HPE Cray Power Management counters provided by the HPE Cray Baseboard Management Controller (BMC). The Slurm “pm_counters” energy plugin⁴ combines the data from all compute nodes involved in each job to produce an overall node energy use for the job which is stored in the Slurm accounting database in the “ConsumedEnergyRaw” and “ConsumedEnergy” fields. The node energy use covers all components in the compute node, including processors, memory, interconnect cards and other parts.

The energy usage by system components external to compute nodes is not currently included or accounted for in the energy use data. Items not accounted for include the interconnect switches, file systems and other parts external to the compute nodes (e.g. cooling infrastructure). The energy use by these components per-job will be substantially less than the energy use for the compute nodes themselves as indicated by the power profile information for ARCHER2 included in Section 2 above.

We obtain the per-job node energy use data (along with the other required job information) from Slurm by querying the accounting database directly and then use a Python program to analyse the data. The research area categorisation is taken from the per-project information contained in the EPCC SAFE database. The analysis scripts are available as part of the open dataset released along with this report⁵. The data fields that are taken from the ARCHER2 Slurm accounting database are:

- *JobIDRaw* - The unique job step ID
- *JobName* - The job step name - for Slurm job steps launched using srun (all parallel job steps on ARCHER2) this contains the executable name
- *Account* - On ARCHER2 this corresponds to the project budget code
- *NNodes* - Number of compute nodes used by the job step
- *NTasks* - Number of parallel processes launched fo the job step
- *ElapsedRaw* - The job step runtime in seconds
- *State* - The final state of the job step (indicates if the job step completed successfully or not)
- *ConsumedEnergyRaw* - The total node energy used by the job step in joules
- *MaxRSS* - Maximum memory use - not used in this analysis
- *AvgRSS* - Mean memory use - not used in this analysis

When read by the Python analysis script, these fields are stored in a Pandas dataframe and some additional fields are generated:

⁴ https://github.com/SchedMD/slurm/tree/master/src/plugins/acct_gather_energy/pm_counters

⁵ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7128646>

- *Energy* - Converts ConsumedEnergyRaw to kWh and marks those job steps that are missing energy data
- *NodePower* - Computes mean compute node power draw in Watts from the Energy and ElapsedRaw fields
- *CPN* (Cores per Node) - Calculates the number of cores used per compute node
- *Cores* - Total cores used
- *Software* - Software package used for the job step - derived from the executable name in JobName matched against a regex library of known applications
- *Motif* - Computational motifs associated with the job step - derived from the identified software package
- *Area* - The research area associated with the job step - derived from the project code in the Account field and the mapping from project code to research area taken from EPCC SAFE

Finally, the analysis script produces the summary of the ARCHER2 job step data used for the analysis below.

DiRAC COSMA

On COSMA, the total cumulative energy consumed by a node is measured at the start and end of each job submitted to the batch scheduler, on each node on which that job runs. The difference between these measurements then gives the total compute energy used by this job. It should be noted that this does not include energy consumed by the fabric (InfiniBand), the storage file systems, or other surrounding infrastructure (login nodes, etc). On a quarterly basis, the job energy information is then disseminated to users and project PIs, informing them of their compute energy usage during that quarter, and using averaged carbon intensity measurements, the approximate gCO₂ that their jobs or project has generated.

The energy measurements are taken using a modified version of ipmitool which captures the data from the motherboard management system. This measures the total power consumption of the node. Modification of ipmitool is necessary to preserve the precision captured from the motherboard.

Current COSMA8 nodes have a bug in the bios that overestimates energy consumption by 50%, so we include a correction for this. We have notified Dell, and they are fixing it in a future BIOS release.

4. Results

ARCHER2

The node energy use and node hours used for jobs in the period 1 December 2021 to 31 July 2022 has been analysed. Due to an issue with the energy counters on some compute nodes that was not rectified until early July 2022, a number of job steps did not have any energy use recorded against them. Table 1 shows the % of job steps and % node hour use that are missing energy use data for each month in the analysis period. Job steps that used large numbers of nodes were disproportionately affected by this issue as the more nodes used, the higher the chance that the job step hit a problematic node. Due to this issue, we present two analyses - one for the full period and one for just July 2022 where the amount of node hour use excluded is much lower than for other months. In both cases, job steps with no energy use were excluded from the analysis so that we are comparing the same job steps for both the energy use and the node hour use.

Table 1: Impact of missing energy data from job steps broken down by month. Numbers indicate what percentage of job steps and nodeh usage are excluded each month from the analysis.

Month	% Job steps	% Node hour use
Dec 2021	0.44%	15.52%
Jan 2022	0.51%	17.21%
Feb 2022	0.64%	13.31%
Mar 2022	1.18%	18.39%
Apr 2022	0.75%	23.59%
May 2022	1.72%	27.73%
Jun 2022	1.68%	12.49%
Jul 2022	0.05%	1.41%

Breakdown by research area

First, we examine the breakdown of energy use and node hour use by research area.

For the period Dec 2021 - Jul 2022, the top ten areas by energy use contribute over 90% of the total energy use on the system and over 90% of the node hour use, so further analysis will focus on these areas. Figure 1 plots the % energy use and % node hour use for these eleven areas and the full data is shown in Table 2. As expected, there is a close correspondence between node hour use and energy use - the more compute resources you use, the more energy you use. However, there are some cases where the energy use is more or less than would be expected based on the node hour use, in particular:

- **Climate Science** has a significantly lower energy use than node hour use: energy use is around 20% lower than node hour use
- **Combustion** has a significantly higher energy use than node hour use: energy use is around 10% higher than node hour use
- **Astrophysics and Cosmology** have a significantly lower energy use than node hour use: energy use is around 20% lower than node hour use

As noted above, the missing energy data for some months in the long period raises the concern that the analysis may be skewed by the missing data. To test this, we also show the breakdown by area for just July 2022 in Table 3 (July 2022 has a very low amount of missing data as the bug that caused the data omission had been fixed by the time this data was gathered). This dataset shows similar features to the full dataset, providing confidence that these are real features and not due to missing energy use data. Table 3 also includes the median node power draw per research area - as would be expected, the research areas with low energy use relative to nodeh use have a lower median node power draw. This can typically happen when the software is not using all of the compute resources on a node. Reasons for this may include making more memory available per core or making more memory bandwidth available per core.

Figure 1: Comparison of % Nodeh use and % Energy use for top 10 research areas (by usage) for the period Dec 2021 - Jul 2022 on ARCHER2. Labels indicate the difference between energy use and nodeh use as a percentage of energy use.

Table 2: Breakdown of percentage energy use and node hour use by research area on ARCHER2 for the period Dec 2021 - Jul 2022.

Research Area	% Energy Use	% Node Hour Use	% Node Hour Use (incl. Job steps without energy data)
Overall	100.0	100.0	100.0
Materials Science	52.1	52.3	50.1
Computational Fluid Dynamics	12.4	11.9	14.4
Climate Science	5.3	6.3	6.4
Combustion	5.1	4.5	4.2
Plasma Physics	4.0	3.7	3.3
Geophysics and Seismology	3.8	3.9	4.1
Biomolecular Modelling	3.5	3.5	3.1
Ocean Science	2.9	2.9	2.7
Surface Science	2.0	1.7	1.6
Mesoscale Engineering	1.9	2.0	1.8
Astrophysics and Cosmology	1.8	2.2	2.2
HPC Research	1.0	0.8	1.2
European projects (no research area available)	1.0	0.9	1
Nuclear Physics	0.8	0.9	0.9
Biochemistry	0.5	0.5	0.4
Medical Science	0.4	0.4	0.8
Support projects	0.3	0.3	0.8
Particle Physics	0.3	0.4	0.3
Soft Matter Physics	0.3	0.2	0.2
Environmental Modelling	0.1	0.1	0.1
Solid State Physics	0.1	0.1	0

Table 3: Breakdown of energy use, node hour use and median node power use by research area on ARCHER2 for the period Jul 2022. The median node power use is a weighted median with the weights given by nodeh use.

Research Area	% Energy Use	% Node Hour Use	% Node Hour Use (incl. Job steps without energy data)	Median Node Power Use (W)
Overall	100.0	100.0	100.0	490
Materials Science	45.9	46.2	45.9	473
Computational Fluid Dynamics	17.8	15.9	16.4	518
Biomolecular Modelling	7.2	6.7	6.5	512
Climate Science	6.5	7.6	7.7	431
Combustion	5.1	4.6	4.8	517
Plasma Physics	4.6	4.6	4.7	493
Ocean Science	3.5	3.4	3.3	494
Geophysics and Seismology	1.8	1.5	1.8	413
Surface Science	1.8	1.6	1.6	508
Astrophysics and Cosmology	1.7	3.2	3.3	242
Particle Physics	1.2	1.2	1.2	465
Mesoscale Engineering	1.1	1.0	1.0	494
HPC Research	0.5	0.4	0.4	489
Biochemistry	0.5	0.4	0.5	530
Soft Matter Physics	0.5	0.4	0.4	528
Support projects	0.3	0.3	0.3	296
Nuclear Physics	0.1	0.2	0.2	89
Chemistry	0.1	0.1	0.1	519
Training	0.1	0.1	0.1	514

Breakdown by software

To get further insight into the different energy use profiles by different research areas, we have also broken the usage down by software. Figure 2 and Table 4 show this breakdown for the longer period (Dec 2021 - Jul 2022).

For the research areas identified as having interesting features in the previous discussion we have investigated which software packages are associated with the groupings:

- **Climate Science:** >90% of usage is attributed to the UK Met Office Unified Model
- **Combustion:** ~70% of usage is attributed to SENGAs and ~20% to OpenFOAM
- **Astrophysics and cosmology:** this usage is associated with a user-compiled code that we do not currently have any further details on

Figure 2: Comparison of % Nodeh use and % Energy use for software for the period Dec 2021 - Jul 2022 on ARCHER2. Labels indicate the difference between energy use and nodeh use as a percentage of energy use.

Met Office Unified Model

We can clearly see that this software uses less energy than would be expected if there were a 1:1 correspondence between node hours used and energy used. Profiling would be needed to understand where this effect comes from but one suggestion is that there is a significant fraction of the application that is I/O bound. When performing I/O operations, time is used (leading to nodeh usage) but the amount of processing required is lower - leading to a corresponding reduction in energy use per unit of time.

Table 4: Breakdown of percentage energy use and node hour use by software on ARCHER2 for the period Dec 2021 - Jul 2022.

Software	% Energy Use	% Node Hour Use	% Node Hour Use (incl. Job steps without energy data)
VASP	33.5	33.3	32.4
cp2k	6.3	6.9	6.3
Met Office UM	3.8	4.7	4.9
CASTEP	4.1	4.5	4.3
Gromacs	3.7	3.5	3.1
LAMMPS	2.9	2.9	2.7
SENGA	3.3	2.7	2.6
PDNS3D	3.4	2.7	3.2
NEMO	2.4	2.3	2.2
ChemShell	2.0	2.3	2.0
iIMB	1.9	1.7	1.6
Python	1.6	1.5	1.6
OpenFOAM	1.6	1.5	1.3
FHI aims	1.4	1.2	1.1
Nektar++	1.4	1.2	1.4
ONETEP	1.2	1.2	1.0
Xcompact3d	1.2	1.2	1.1
CASINO	1.2	1.1	1.0

SENGA

SENGA shows the opposite trend to the Met Office UM - more energy is used per unit of time than would be expected if there were a 1:1 correspondence between nodeh usage and energy use. Previous studies have noted that in cases where an application is memory bound the energy use can be artificially increased as cores on the compute node can make use of turbo-boost capabilities to increase the power draw and, hence, the energy use. Profiling work would need to be undertaken to understand if this is the explanation for the SENGA profile. It is worth noting that previous studies⁶ have also suggested that the turbo-boost does not provide any

⁶M. Bareford, N. Johnson, M. Weiland, *EASC '16: Proceedings of the Exascale Applications and Software Conference 2016*, 6, p1 <https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/2938615.2938619>

significant improvement in performance so, for applications with these characteristics, it may be possible to reduce the energy use without impacting performance. Work is ongoing on ARCHER2 to characterise application performance as a function of processor clock speed (which impacts energy use).

OpenFOAM

OpenFOAM shows less pronounced differences between energy use and nodeh use but is skewed in the same direction as SENGA and, as the application is of a similar type to SENGA, it may well be subject to the same explanation for the difference.

DiRAC COSMA

We have broken down the energy usage by DiRAC project, for Q2 2022 in Table 4.

As can be seen, there is a wide range of average power usage per node, from 210 W to 860 W. We are making some investigations into this, in particular, between two codes which perform very similar tasks. We suspect that the lowest power/node comes from codes not being used correctly, e.g. submitting a single core job to a full node, while the highest power/node is for jobs that are either CPU intensive (i.e. no I/O) or MPI processes which spin or poll while waiting for data (rather than being interrupt-based). There are often MPI flags which can be set to tune this behaviour. The largest project, dp004, has used nearly 260 MWh during this quarter, or 120 kWh per hour (i.e. an average power consumption of 120 kW).

We do not break these projects into specific codes used, as many of these are custom or in-house codes. However, for larger projects such as dp004 and dp203, it is known that SWIFT and GADGET4 are significant contributors to the results. Both of these are cosmological codes.

Table 4: Breakdown of energy use, node hour use and mean node power use by project on DiRAC COSMA8 for the period Apr-Jun 2022.

Project	Energy used / kWh	Time used / node hours	Average power per node / W
do006:	47.0	120.7	389.3
do009:	2725.0	10960.4	248.6
dp002:	73.3	313.7	233.8
dp004:	258966.0	795906.0	325.4
dp012:	24526.8	102087.0	240.3
dp016:	27546.1	42190.7	652.9
dp019:	12482.2	18445.7	676.7
dp034:	26536.8	36929.8	718.6
dp036:	8842.9	12692.7	696.7
dp040:	3144.2	4181.2	752.0
dp050:	3541.2	11739.9	301.6
dp058:	5484.6	22628.9	242.4
dp092:	12750.3	60952.8	209.2
dp104:	17053.3	32280.6	528.3
dp128:	3831.3	14362.4	266.8
dp155:	473.6	716.6	660.9
dp162:	2338.1	2709.0	863.1
dp193:	11903.3	18220.8	653.3
dp195:	349.9	836.3	418.4
dp203:	124369.0	228978.0	543.2
dp206:	632.1	1472.9	429.2
dp209:	614.0	888.2	691.3
dp210:	1759.4	2270.0	775.1
dp212:	3583.7	4777.4	750.1
dp217:	15263.2	34192.8	446.4
dp219:	2439.9	4337.6	562.5
dp221:	3265.4	4081.9	800.0
dr004:	21.8	28.2	774.4

5. Conclusions and next steps

The main aim of this initial work in the HPC-JEEP project is to understand if the energy use data we have available from HPC systems such as ARCHER2 and COSMA are able to provide the basis for useful insights and analyses of the energy use (and, potentially, emissions) of different research areas and software on the systems. It is clear that the per-job node energy use data available on current HPC systems is able to provide data that can support analysis to help understand impacts of decisions around energy use on different user communities.

Furthermore, we have been able to develop analysis tooling that can use raw data from the Slurm scheduler and IPMI power monitoring to produce useful analyses and, for COSMA, start to provide energy use data back to users. It is also useful to note that the initial analysis of power draw by service components shows that the compute node energy use is by far the most important component of energy use by jobs on HPC systems: on both ARCHER2 and COSMA, the compute nodes account for over 80% of the power draw of the services. Although understanding energy use per job of other components is potentially interesting, they will not actually have much impact on the conclusions drawn using node energy data on its own. The idle power draw of compute nodes on ARCHER2 (200 to 250 W) is high compared to the idle power draw on COSMA8 (150 W) and, as part of the ARCHER2 Case Study activity we are working to understand this difference.

We can already envisage how such data could potentially be used by service operators to make decisions on how services could be provided. For example:

- Use cases/applications that are energy dense per unit of time (e.g. Combustion research on ARCHER2) could potentially be preferentially scheduled to run when more free cooling is available (e.g. overnight or during the colder months of the year) to reduce the cooling overheads for the service during warmer periods.
- Regional carbon intensity forecasts for the energy supply to large scale HPC facilities could be used to reduce emissions by preferentially scheduling high energy density usage during periods of forecast low carbon intensity (e.g. when a high proportion of electricity comes from wind power) and preferentially scheduling low energy density usage when the forecast carbon intensity is higher.
- During extreme heat events where cooling large HPC systems can become difficult, use of the service (or a portion of the service) could be limited to those software/research areas that are less energy dense. This would preserve the utilisation and impact of the services without requiring nodes to be taken out of service.

Design and implementation of such policies on systems such as ARCHER2 and COSMA is obviously interesting but is beyond the scope of the HPC-JEEP project.

It is also clear that a better understanding of why different applications have different energy density profiles and what the performance variability is when the energy draw is capped is required to make operational decisions and to provide useful advice to researchers on how they

can be energy-efficient in their use of HPC systems. Work in this area is going on in parallel as part of the ARCHER2 Case Study activity.

Future UKRI HPC resource allocations may be based on an energy or emissions allowance, rather than on core-hours as is used previously. By making researchers aware of their energy consumption (or emissions), they will be able to plan for this change, and predict the likely allocations they will need to request. This will encourage codes to be developed more efficiently, as it will allow more science to be obtained from a given allocation. Future work as part of the HPC-JEEP project will assess charging by energy/emissions use on HPC facilities: particularly the impact on different research communities/projects and what metrics need to be made available to researchers and project principal investigators ahead of such a change to allow them to understand their energy use and efficiency.

As part of the ongoing work to gain a deeper understanding of the energy use characteristics of these large-scale HPC services, additional information is required. In particular, the analysis in this report does not include any impact of plant-level overheads (e.g. external cooling requirements, uninterruptible power supplies (UPS), efficiency loss due to internal power distribution). It may be that these factors do not add significant overheads or are only of significant interest for particular restricted time periods (e.g. periods of high external air temperatures), but they do need to be measured and analysed for their impact to be understood. Again, it is beyond the scope of HPC-JEEP to investigate these aspects though, for ARCHER2, these are being investigated as part of the ARCHER2 Case Study activity.

The next steps for this project are:

- WP2: Propose a charging scheme based on energy use (and, if time allows, emissions) and recompute charges for projects/research areas/software based on the proposed scheme. Analyse the potential impacts of this new charging scheme on different user communities.
- WP3: Propose metrics to communicate to different stakeholders the node energy use and Scope 2 emissions associated with this node energy use that can support operational decisions around HPC facilities in the journey to Net Zero. COSMA is already providing data back to users on their compute node energy use and estimated emissions. We plan to supplement this with energy use data from fabric, storage and cooling and seek feedback from users on this approach.

Both of these pieces of work will be available as technical reports from HPC-JEEP in due course.